

Impact of Solvent Polarity on the Photoinduced Dynamics of a Push-Pull Molecular Motor

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Supporting Information

Contents

S1 QD-NEVPT2 quantum chemical calculations	2
S2 Comparison of exchange-correlation functionals	4
S3 Comparison of results for 1c and 1'c	4
S4 Semiempirical electronic structure method	8
S5 Preparation of the QM/MM system and ground-state thermal equilibrations	10
S6 Fitting functions	15
S7 Simulation of time-resolved emission	15
S8 Hydrogen bond analysis	16
S9 Supplementary tables	18
S10 Supplementary figures	18

S1 QD-NEVPT2 quantum chemical calculations

To benchmark the MRSF-TDDFT method for our investigated push-pull motor, we performed ab initio electronic structure calculations using the quasi-degenerate n-electron valence second-order perturbation theory (QD-NEVPT2) method¹⁻³. In particular, we computed the energies of the three lowest singlet states S_0 - S_2 at different DFT/MRSF-TDDFT optimized geometries: (i) the **1c** S_0 minimum, (ii) the two S_1 minima, namely min_1 and min_2 , and (iii) the lowest S_1/S_0 minimum-energy conical intersection CoIn_1 .

The QD-NEVPT2 calculations were based on complete active space self-consistent field (CASSCF) wavefunctions computed using an active space of 12 electrons in 12 molecular orbitals (CAS(12,12)) and the state-averaged approach comprising the three lowest singlet states (S_0 - S_2). Moreover, we used the strongly-contracted formulation of the NEVPT2 method² and a quasi-degenerate (QD) scheme based on the Van Vleck perturbation theory⁴. All the QD-NEVPT2 calculations were performed using the cc-pVDZ basis set⁵ and the ORCA quantum chemistry software (Version 5.0.4)⁶.

In Table S1, we report the relative energies of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition energy, as well as the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ dipoles, computed with the QD-NEVPT2 method. For comparison, in the same table the corresponding energies and dipoles computed at the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP level are also reported. Figure S1 shows the natural orbitals of the active space obtained in the CASSCF calculation for isomer **1c**.

Table S1: Energies of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states (relative to the **1c** S_0 minimum), $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition energies (ΔE_{01} , ΔE_{02}), and transition dipoles (μ_{01} , μ_{02}) for the **1c** S_0 minimum, the twisted S_1 minima min_1 and min_2 , and the lowest S_1/S_0 minimum-energy conical intersection CoIn_1 of motor **1**, computed with the QD-NEVPT2 and MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP methods. Energies are reported in eV, dipole (modulus) in Debye.

Structure	Method	S_0	S_1	ΔE_{01}	μ_{01}	S_2	ΔE_{02}	μ_{02}
1c (S_0 -min)	QD-NEVPT2	0.00	3.26	3.26	5.943	4.37	4.37	1.070
	MRSF-TDDFT	0.00	3.37	3.37	8.418	3.99	3.99	3.403
1 (S_1 - min_1)	QD-NEVPT2	0.46	3.01	2.54	7.805	3.74	3.28	1.334
	MRSF-TDDFT	0.40	3.03	2.64	10.169	3.66	3.27	1.251
1 (S_1 - min_2)	QD-NEVPT2	2.32	2.99	0.67	1.994	4.78	2.46	0.818
	MRSF-TDDFT	1.95	2.51	0.55	1.878	4.25	2.30	1.082
1 (CoIn_1)	QD-NEVPT2	3.30	3.47	0.17	-	5.56	2.27	-
	MRSF-TDDFT	3.00	3.03	0.03	-	5.16	2.16	-

Figure S1: State-averaged natural orbitals of the active space for the QD-NEVPT2 calculation of isomer **1c** at its B3LYP/cc-pVDZ optimized S_0 geometry. The dashed line separates the orbitals with occupation numbers close to 2 (above) and close to 0 (below).

S2 Comparison of exchange-correlation functionals

Table S2: Energies of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states (relative to the $\mathbf{1c}$ S_0 minimum), $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition energies (ΔE_{01} , ΔE_{02}), and transition dipoles (μ_{01} , μ_{02}) for the $\mathbf{1c}$ S_0 minimum and the twisted S_1 minima min_1 and min_2 of motor $\mathbf{1}$, computed with the MRSF-TDDFT method using the CAM-B3LYP and BHHLYP functionals, and the cc-pVDZ basis set. For $\mathbf{1c}$ (S_0 -min), the MRSF-TDDFT calculations were performed at the DFT/B3LYP/cc-pVDZ optimized geometry for both functionals and the QD-NEVPT2 results, computed at the same geometry (Section S1), are also reported for comparison. For the S_1 minima, the geometries were optimized at the MRSF-TDDFT level with the two different functionals. Energies are reported in eV, dipole (modulus) in Debye.

Structure	Functional	S_0	S_1	ΔE_{01}	μ_{01}	S_2	ΔE_{02}	μ_{02}
$\mathbf{1c}$ (S_0 -min)	CAM-B3LYP	0.00	3.37	3.37	8.418	3.99	3.99	3.403
	BHHLYP	0.00	3.43	3.43	8.109	4.06	4.06	3.306
	QD-NEVPT2	0.00	3.26	3.26	5.943	4.37	4.37	1.070
$\mathbf{1}$ (S_1 - min_1)	CAM-B3LYP	0.40	3.03	2.64	10.169	3.66	3.27	1.251
	BHHLYP	0.24	2.98	2.74	9.321	3.65	3.41	1.424
$\mathbf{1}$ (S_1 - min_2)	CAM-B3LYP	1.95	2.51	0.55	1.878	4.25	2.30	1.082
	BHHLYP	1.77	2.41	0.64	1.464	4.07	2.29	0.524

S3 Comparison of results for $\mathbf{1c}$ and $\mathbf{1'c}$

Table S3: Selected geometrical parameters of the ground-state (S_0) minimum-energy isomers $\mathbf{1c}$ (push-pull motor) and $\mathbf{1'c}$ (unsubstituted motor), computed at the DFT/B3LYP level. Atomic distances are reported in Å, dihedral angles in degrees. The definition of geometrical parameters is provided in the main text (Figure 1a).

Structure	r	θ	φ	φ'	α	α'	β	β'
$\mathbf{1c}$ (S_0 -min)	1.365	4.3	2.3	2.7	34.0	35.6	29.5	30.2
$\mathbf{1'c}$ (S_0 -min)	1.363	4.0	2.6	2.6	35.3	35.3	30.1	30.1

Table S4: Vertical excitation energies (eV), transition dipoles (modulus in Debye, D) and main electronic configurations for the S_1 and S_2 states of $\mathbf{1c}$ (push-pull motor) and $\mathbf{1'c}$ (unsubstituted motor), computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP and QD-NEVPT2 methods at the DFT/B3LYP optimized geometries. Only the electronic configurations with a weight larger than 0.10 are reported. In the definition of the electronic configurations, we used H to indicate HOMO and L to indicate LUMO. The results for $\mathbf{1'c}$ (unsubstituted motor) were taken from Ref.⁷.

Method	Structure	State	Energy (eV)	Trans. Dipole (D)	Configuration	Weight
MRSF-TDDFT	$\mathbf{1c}$	S_1	3.37	8.418	$H \rightarrow L$	0.819
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.126
		S_2	3.99	3.403	$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.523
	$\mathbf{1'c}$	S_1	3.65	7.906	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.277
					$H \rightarrow L$	0.922
		S_2	4.21	0.312	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.742
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.194
QD-NEVPT2	$\mathbf{1c}$	S_1	3.26	5.943	$H \rightarrow L$	0.786
					$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.433
		S_2	4.37	1.070	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.197
	$\mathbf{1'c}$	S_1	3.56	5.741	$H \rightarrow L$	0.873
					$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.734
		S_2	4.15	1.279	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.734

Figure S2: Frontier molecular orbitals for **1c** (push-pull motor) and **1'c** (unsubstituted motor), computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method at the DFT/B3LYP optimized ground-state geometries.

Figure S3: **a** Potential energy paths between selected optimized geometries for motors **1** (solid lines) and **1'** (dashed lines), computed using the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method. The paths $1c/1'c \rightarrow S_1$ -min₁ and S_1 -min₂ \rightarrow CoIn₁ were obtained by geodesic interpolation, while the S_1 -min₁ \rightarrow S_1 -min₂ pathway is a minimum-energy path on the S_1 state. The potential energies (eV) of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states, as well as the S_1 - S_0 energy gap, are shown. **b** Transition dipoles (modulus in Debye) from S_0 to the S_1 and S_2 states along the paths. **c** Selected geometrical parameters.

S4 Semiempirical electronic structure method

In the semiempirical FOMO-CI calculations, we used the AM1 parameters optimized for the unsubstituted motor **1'** in Ref.⁷ for all sp² carbon atoms of **1**, while we employed the standard AM1 parameters⁸ for all hydrogen, sp³ or sp carbon, nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the motor. In Table S5, we compare the semiempirical FOMO-CI results, computed using the aforementioned combination of parameters (R-AM1), with the the DFT/B3LYP and MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP reference data of the S₀-S₂ state energies, transition dipoles from S₀ and selected geometrical parameters for the **1c**, S₁ minima and S₁/S₀ minimum-energy conical intersection CoIn₁ geometries of the push-pull motor **1**.

Table S5: Target data and the corresponding semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CI values for the S₀-S₂ state energies (E , in eV), transition dipoles (μ , in Debye) and selected geometrical parameters (\AA , deg.) of the push-pull motor **1**. The state energies are reported relative to the **1c** S₀ minimum. Geometrical parameters are defined in the main text (Figure 1a).

Structure	Variable	Target	R-AM1
1c	$E(S_0)$	0.00	0.00
	$E(S_1)$	3.37	3.51
	$E(S_2)$	4.00	4.16
	$\mu(S_0 \rightarrow S_1)$	8.418	7.556
	$\mu(S_0 \rightarrow S_2)$	3.404	2.023
	r	1.365	1.356
	θ	4.3	0.2
	φ	2.3	3.5
	φ'	2.7	3.7
	α	34.0	36.8
	α'	35.6	36.7
	β	29.5	23.2
β'	30.2	23.2	
S ₁ -min ₁	$E(S_0)$	0.40	0.50
	$E(S_1)$	3.03	3.06
	$E(S_2)$	3.66	3.37
	$\mu(S_0 \rightarrow S_1)$	10.169	8.439
	r	1.411	1.408
	θ	24.2	35.7
	φ	-0.2	1.4
	φ'	-0.2	1.5
	α	20.4	19.3
	α'	21.7	20.2

	β	27.0	13.8
	β'	27.1	14.4
S ₁ -min ₂	$E(S_0)$	1.95	1.61
	$E(S_1)$	2.51	2.58
	$E(S_2)$	4.25	3.67
	$\mu(S_0 \rightarrow S_1)$	1.878	1.375
	r	1.466	1.406
	θ	79.7	89.6
	φ	0.4	0.1
	φ'	10.8	4.2
	α	-4.7	-3.6
	α'	9.1	5.0
	β	-6.6	-4.5
	β'	-25.4	-1.6
	CoIn ₁	$E(S_0)$	3.00
$E(S_1)$		3.03	3.14
r		1.455	1.386
θ		66.4	59.1
φ		-2.4	-2.1
φ'		21.4	25.2
α		-12.8	-13.5
α'		40.7	52.1
β		-10.2	-11.2
β'	-6.8	-7.7	

S5 Preparation of the QM/MM system and ground-state thermal equilibrations

For each investigated solvent, the starting coordinates for the QM/MM ground-state thermal equilibrations were sampled from a classical MM trajectory at constant temperature of our investigated motor **1** (**1c** conformer) embedded in a cubic box of solvent molecules, with a box side of 50.0 Å and periodic boundary conditions. The initial cubic box was prepared using the PACKMOL package⁹. The MM trajectory was propagated using the Berendsen thermostat¹⁰ for 0.5 ns, with a time step of 2.0 fs and a temperature of 300 K. In the MM simulations, both the motor and the solvent molecules were treated using the OPLS-AA force field¹¹. The MM trajectory was computed using the TINKER 8.5 package¹².

For each solvent, five snapshots (atomic coordinates) were sampled from the last 0.25 ns of the MM trajectory, which was divided into five distinct and consecutive time intervals and for each interval one snapshot was randomly sampled. Next, for each selected snapshot, a spherical cluster of solvent molecules around the motor was extracted from the cubic periodic box using a cut-off distance of 25.0 Å from the motor. Then, five QM/MM ground-state thermal trajectories were propagated, each for 10 ps, using the Bussi-Parrinello stochastic thermostat¹³, with a temperature of 300 K and a time step of 0.5 fs. To preserve the spherical cluster during the QM/MM simulations, a spherical harmonic potential with a radius of 25.0 Å from the origin of the Cartesian coordinate system was imposed on the MM solvent molecules. The QM/MM trajectories were computed using the MOPAC-PI package¹⁴ interfaced with TINKER 8.5¹².

Figures S4-S7 show the time evolution of the QM/MM potential energy, the total kinetic energy, the temperature of the QM subsystem (i.e. the motor), and the S₁ and S₂ excitation energies, obtained in the QM/MM ground-state thermal equilibrations in cyclohexane and methanol. For each QM/MM trajectory, the last 3 ps were employed to sample the initial conditions for the surface hopping simulations.

Figure S4: Time evolution of the potential and kinetic energies (in a.u.) obtained in the ground-state QM/MM thermal equilibrations for **1c** in cyclohexane. In each panel, the moving average, computed for time intervals of 250 fs, is also shown (pink and cyan colors for potential and kinetic energies, respectively).

Figure S5: Time evolution of the temperature (in K) of the QM subsystem and of the S_1 and S_2 excitation energies (in eV) obtained in the ground-state QM/MM thermal equilibrations for **1c** in cyclohexane. For the QM temperature, both the time evolution and the moving average, computed for time intervals of 250 fs, are shown (blue and cyan colors, respectively), while for the excitation energies only the moving averages are shown.

Figure S6: Time evolution of the potential and kinetic energies (in a.u.) obtained in the ground-state QM/MM thermal equilibrations for **1c** in methanol. In each panel, the moving average, computed for time intervals of 250 fs, is also shown (pink and cyan colors for potential and kinetic energies, respectively).

Figure S7: Time evolution of the temperature (in K) of the QM subsystem and of the S_1 and S_2 excitation energies (in eV) obtained in the ground-state QM/MM thermal equilibrations for **1c** in methanol. For the QM temperature, both the time evolution and the moving average, computed for time intervals of 250 fs, are shown (blue and cyan colors, respectively), while for the excitation energies only the moving averages are shown.

S6 Fitting functions

The S_1 population decay obtained from the SH simulations was fitted with the following function:

$$\begin{cases} P_{S_1}(t) = 1, & \text{for } t < t_0 \\ P_{S_1}(t) = e^{-(t-t_0)/\tau_1}, & \text{for } t \geq t_0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where t_0 is a delay time and τ_1 is the time constant of excited-state decay. The excited-state lifetime is given by $t_0 + \tau_1$.

To fit the time-resolved fluorescence emission computed along the SH simulations, we used a triple-exponential function:

$$I(t) = I_0 [w_1 e^{-t/\tau_1} + w_2 e^{-t/\tau_2} + (1 - w_1 - w_2) e^{-t/\tau_3}] \quad (\text{S2})$$

where I_0 is the fluorescence intensity at the initial time ($t = 0$), τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3 are time constants of fluorescence decay, and w_1 , w_2 and $w_3 = 1 - w_1 - w_2$ are the corresponding weights.

S7 Simulation of time-resolved emission

In the SH simulations presented in this work, the time-resolved total fluorescence emission intensity, averaged over all SH trajectories, is computed using the following formula, as implemented in the MOPAC-PI package¹⁴:

$$I_{tot}(t) = \frac{1}{N_T} \sum_{k=1}^{N_T} \sum_{i=0}^{j-1} A_{ji}^{(k)} = \frac{4}{3\hbar^4 c^3} \frac{1}{N_T} \sum_{k=1}^{N_T} \sum_{i=0}^{j-1} [\Delta E_{ij}^3 \mu_{ij}^2]^{(k)} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where N_T is the total number of SH trajectories, A_{ji} is the Einstein coefficient for spontaneous emission due to a radiative transition from the electronic state j to i , k is the trajectory index, j is the current (active) state for trajectory k at time t , ΔE_{ij} is the energy difference between states i and j , μ_{ij} is the corresponding transition dipole, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum, and the superscript (k) indicate the dependence on the trajectory k and on time (i.e. A_{ji} and all the quantities in square brackets depend on k and time). In practice, Eq. S3 corresponds to averaging over all SH trajectories the sum of Einstein coefficients $\sum_{i=0}^{j-1} A_{ji}$, where j is the current state of the trajectory and A_{ji} is defined, within the dipole approximation of light-molecule interaction, as:

$$A_{ji} = \frac{4}{3\hbar^4 c^3} \Delta E_{ij}^3 \mu_{ij}^2. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Specifically, Eq. S4 gives the probability of spontaneous emission of a photon per unit of time, due to a radiative transition from the electronic state j to i .

S8 Hydrogen bond analysis

Table S6: Fraction and corresponding percentage (%) of structures with a hydrogen bond between the -CN group of the QM motor and the -OH group of one MM methanol molecule at the starting geometries (Time = 0) and those of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations for **1c** in methanol (MeOH). For the identification of a hydrogen bond, two different thresholds for the maximum N–O distance were considered, i.e. 3.0 Å and 3.5 Å. In both cases, a threshold of 150° for the minimum N–H–O angle was employed.

Geometries	Hydrogen bonds	
	$\text{dist}(\text{N}-\text{O}) \leq 3.0 \text{ \AA}$	$\text{dist}(\text{N}-\text{O}) \leq 3.5 \text{ \AA}$
Time = 0	12/105 (11.4%)	18/105 (17.1%)
$S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops	25/105 (23.8%)	36/105 (34.3%)

Figure S8: Populations of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states for **1c** in methanol, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations including all trajectories (All traj.) and only the trajectories where no hydrogen bond is present at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries (No H-bond). For the identification of a hydrogen bond, two different thresholds for the maximum N–O distance were considered, i.e. 3.0 Å (panel **a**) and 3.5 Å (panel **b**). In both cases, a threshold of 150° for the minimum N–H–O angle was employed.

Figure S9: Distributions of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (in eV) for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and those of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations for **1c** in methanol. In each panel, the sub-distributions of geometries where a hydrogen bond (between the QM motor and one methanol molecule) is absent (No H-bond, black color) or present (H-bond, green color) are also shown. For the identification of a hydrogen bond, two different thresholds for the maximum N–O distance were considered, i.e. 3.0 Å (panel a,c) and 3.5 Å (panel b,d). In both cases, a threshold of 150° for the minimum N–H–O angle was employed.

S9 Supplementary tables

Table S7: State energies of S_0 and S_1 , $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition energy (ΔE_{01}), $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole (μ_{01}) of S_1 , and selected internal coordinates of minimum-energy (min), transition state (ts) and S_0/S_1 conical intersection (CoIn) geometries of the investigated push-pull motor **1**, computed at the DFT/B3LYP and MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP levels. Energies are reported in eV, dipoles (modulus) in Debye, atomic distances in Å, dihedral angles in degrees. The state energies of S_0 and S_1 are reported relative to the **1c** S_0 minimum. S_1 -ts₁₂ is the transition state for the pathway S_1 -min₁ \rightarrow S_1 -min₂ on the S_1 PES.

Structure	S_0	S_1	ΔE_{01}	μ_{01}	r	θ	φ	φ'	α	α'	β	β'
1c (S_0 -min)	0.00	3.37	3.37	8.418	1.365	4.3	2.3	2.7	34.0	35.6	29.5	30.2
1 (S_1 -min ₁)	0.40	3.03	2.64	10.169	1.411	24.2	-0.2	-0.2	20.4	21.7	27.0	27.1
1 (S_1 -min ₂)	1.95	2.51	0.55	1.878	1.466	79.7	0.4	10.8	-4.7	9.1	-6.6	-25.4
1 (S_1 -ts ₁₂)	1.95	3.09	1.14	7.529	1.491	60.6	2.3	4.7	5.4	7.8	12.6	6.3
1 (CoIn ₁)	3.00	3.03	0.03	1.016	1.455	66.4	-2.4	21.4	-12.8	40.7	-10.2	-6.8
1tm (S_0 -min)	0.21	3.36	3.15	10.419	1.374	162.7	-4.1	-4.1	-35.5	-35.8	-27.1	-27.8

S10 Supplementary figures

Figure S10: Potential energies (eV) of the S_0 and S_1 states for geodesic interpolations from **1c** and S_1 -min₁ to CoIn₁ of motor **1**, computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method.

Figure S11: Populations of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states for **1c** in gas phase, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations using 40 trajectories and two different time steps (Δt): 0.2 fs and 0.5 fs.

Figure S12: Absorption spectrum of motor **1c**, computed along the ground-state QM/MM thermal equilibrations in cyclohexane and methanol (time interval from 7 ps to 10 ps of 5 QM/MM thermal trajectories, for each solvent, see Section S5). For each spectrum, the contributions of the S_1 and S_2 excited states are shown, along with the energy window (in gold) employed in the sampling of initial conditions for the surface hopping simulations.

Figure S13: Distribution of θ in the S_1 state for different time intervals of the SH simulations for **1c** in cyclohexane (panels a, c, e) and in methanol (panels b, d, f).

Figure S14: Distributions of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (in eV) for the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries and the S_1 minimum-energy geometries of **1c** in cyclohexane (panels **a**, **c**) and in methanol (panels **b**, **d**). In panels **a** and **b**, the θ value of the twisted S_1 minimum (min_2 , dashed grey line), computed at the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) level in gas-phase is also shown.

Figure S15: Distributions of θ for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and the final geometries in the S_0 state (Time = 20 ps) of the SH simulations of **1** in cyclohexane (panel **a**) and in methanol (panel **b**).

Figure S16: Distributions of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ dipole (modulus in Debye) and the dihedrals φ , φ' , β and β' for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, as obtained in the SH simulations of **1** in cyclohexane (panels **a**, **c**, **d**, **g**, **h**) and in methanol (panels **b**, **e**, **f**, **i**, **j**).

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